

IMPROVED INTERFACIAL ADHESION AND MANUFACTURING METHOD OF MGF/P-DCPD COMPOSITES USING W, Mo, OR Ru TYPE CATALYSTS IN AIR CONDITION

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ABSTRACT

Dicyclopentadiene (DCPD) resins are manufactured commercially using Reaction Injection Molding (RIM) process. DCPD has valuable properties with good impact resistance, low temperature resistance and water-resisting. In particular the impact properties are much better than epoxy resins. The application of DCPD resins includes forklift, fork crane, dump truck and heavy vehicles. The manufacturing time need to be reduced and the mechanical properties of DCPD resin also can be improved by adding reinforcement materials. In this work, compression molding method was used to improve mechanical properties of DCPD. The optimum curing conditions of DCPD were investigated with pressure, temperature, and stirring time and speed in the curing conditions. In addition, the mechanical property of DPCD was improved by adding reinforcement such as carbon fiber and glass fiber. After mechanical measurement at different conditions, the optimum curing condition of DCPD resin was obtained as 80~100 C in temperature, 15 psi in pressure, 200 rpm in stirring speed and 70 seconds in stirring time. After adding reinforcement materials such as chop carbon and glass fiber, the DCPD composites exhibited even worse mechanical properties. Surface treatment of reinforcing fibers and modification of DCPD catalysts should be studied continuously.

1. INTRODUCTION

The monomer of dicyclopentadiene (DCPD) has a chemical structure of norbornene and the mechanism of p-DCPD was made with the ring-open reaction by different catalyst effect. The most chemical structure consisted of carbons and it is very stable structure with effective physical property. DCPD is dependent on the physical properties by the catalyst types [1-3]. Tungsten catalyst shows high activity, however, it is difficult to handle and easy to lose activity. In case of the of development of Molybdenum, the activity of the catalyst compared with the Tungsten catalyst was low but easy to use due to chemical stability [4]. The based Tungsten and Molybdenum catalysts have serious disadvantages that must be curing in a nitrogen condition [5]. However, recent Ruthenium catalyst to improve their weakness has been developed [6]. The Ruthenium catalyst was become easy to handle by adjusting the reaction time through solvent. It is commercially difficulty to use because Ruthenium catalyst is much higher price than Molybdenum and Tungsten catalysts [7]. The most important part in developing the commercial resins was a difficult point in the atmosphere curing and a high price. If

it is possible to eliminate, this part can be used as a polymer material for the high-speed curing [8]. The best advantage of the *p*-DCPD had the chemical structure of carbon and the polymer crystalline of high. In case of having a low oxygen functional group, the additive can increase high mechanical properties. Tungsten catalyst showed higher impact strength than other resins [9, 10]. By adding monomer the increased degree of crosslinking of the polymer has been developed to a commercial polymer resins. Ruthenium catalyst has an advantage of high machinability to compare with epoxy resins and it has been a lot of development than the other resins [11]. Method for molding of the *p*-DCPD resins has been used for most of reaction injection molding (RIM) in thermosetting resin of the excellent moldability [12]. When the thermoplastic resin is manufactured using RIM method, the oxygen avoids the contact and it has the advantage of reducing the molding time. The DCPD resin used to cut off the oxygen to RIM reference using Tungsten, Molybdenum catalyst [13, 14]. However, high cost and large space for building the molding equipment is necessary to produce the product for an efficient method. The cure of DCPD resin requires the temperature of about 80 °C, the catalyst activity are retained to possible without RIM process. It proves that the catalyst activity in the resin cannot be easy to disappear. In addition, the resin was formed through open molding method [15, 16]. The DCPD resin was to observe used three type catalysts in the curing and resin analyzed for mechanical properties and moldability of the product. To alternate the RIM in the manufacturing process, DCPD resin tried open molding pressure molding with air condition. The DCPD resin was observed the mechanical properties based on the exposure time and the pressure in air condition. This study tried to analyze stability and crystalline based on catalyst and analyzed the possibilities using milled glass fiber to reinforcement to improve property of DCPD. The most effective DCPD catalyst was checked with different amount and surface treatment of reinforcements, and their interfacial evaluation. Ultimately, the most proper DCPD/catalyst condition are dependent upon both curing DCPD resin in air condition, and the effective analysis on the different catalyst used for DCPD curing conditions.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 MATERIALS

Used DCPD was mainly based on a nature of the material formed during the polymerization of dicyclopentadiene (DCPD), including double bond geometry and cross-link density, is ultimately determined by the catalyst systems which are utilized. Many catalyst systems have been studied for their reactivity in the polymerization of dicyclopentadiene, and it seems that the formation of a linear, soluble polymer is highly dependent upon the choice of transition metal halide. Three catalysts with tungsten (T02, RIMTEC Co., Japan), molybdenum (TELENE 1690A, RIMTEC Co., Japan), and ruthenium (PENTEM 8003ms, RIMTEK Co., Japan), milled glass fiber (MF06JB1-20, Asahi glass Co., Japan) were used. To fabricate milled glass fiber (MGF)/DCPD, the reinforcement put in the DCPD 300g solution was attempted with a mixture. Mixing method was to blend them at a condition 1000rpm using a stirrer, and the precipitation of MGF did not occur. Silane coupling agent for modified MGF was norbornene structure ((5-bicycloheptenyl)-triethoxysilane, Gelest Inc., U. S. A.).

2.2 EVALUATION OF REACTION POLYMERIZATION OF DCPD WITH DIFFERENT CATALYSTS AND OPTIMUM MANUFACTURING CONDITION

Figure 1 shows the DCPD moldability process with RIM and compression molding. The optimum DCPD curing condition was analyzed using different catalysts about mechanical properties, heat of reaction, reaction time. Although the cure of DCPD tried to use RIM process generally, it was not checked the micro voids stable of tungsten catalyst and thus compression molding was used. The cure temperature of all DCPD resin has 80 °C and 300 seconds in air condition. To check the reaction rate of heat of polymerization for each DCPD catalyst, a mixed solution of 100 gram DCPD was analyzed from room to curing temperature. In addition, the optimum curing of the DCPD was checked by the difference of pressure degree at open molding. DCPD resin in catalyst of activity was checked because this specimen was fabricated in air. After specimen was cured completely, the mechanical properties and fracture surface were evaluated to obtain the maximum exposure time.

Figure 1: Manufacturing method of DCPD materials: (a) RIM; (b) compression molding.

2.3 THERMAL, MECHANICAL AND INTERFACIAL PROPERTY OF P-DCPD

Mechanical properties and thermal properties of DCPD were measured with the types of the used 3 catalysts, W, Mo, and Ru comparatively. Thermo gravimetric analysis (TGA) and a differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was used to check thermal weight change and glass transition temperature, T_g . Tensile, bending, compression were to evaluate mechanical properties by prepared with standard specimens based on American Society of Testing Materials (ASTM). Finally to evaluate interfacial adhesion between DCPD and the MGF was performed with contact angle measurement and microdroplet test.

It is possible to analyze the surface energy of the material using the contact angle measurement. Using a static contact angle method the changes in surface energy of DCPD catalysts were obtained. [17]. Based on the surface energy of the material the work of adhesion between the reinforcement material and DCPD resin was obtained to predict improved interfacial adhesion. From the long glass fiber microdroplet was made to fabricate the droplet on glass fiber. Depending on different catalysts the interfacial shear strength (IFSS) were changed. The IFSS was determined by the microdroplet pull-out test as described previously. The embedded length of the resin droplet on a single carbon fiber was approximately 150 μm . The IFSS was calculated from the measured pullout force, F , using the following equation [18]:

$$IFSS = \frac{F}{\pi D_f L} \quad [1]$$

where D_f and L are the diameter and the embedded length of the fiber in the matrix. A UTM was used to “pull-out” the resin drop on the glass fiber at a test speed of 0.5 mm/min. Fracture surface of MGF reinforced DCPD composites was observed to check the interface between MGF and DCPD and uniform dispersion state using FE-SEM.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 CHEMICAL REACTION OF P-DCPD MATERIALS WITH DIFFERENT CATALYSTS

Figure 2: NMR results of DCPD condition with different ring open chemical structures.

Figure 2 summarizes the results of the step by step reaction of DCPD of tungsten catalyst using nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR). In the initial stage the peak of the norbornene can be shown to be changed with the ring open reaction. Since aromatic group is very stable and have complicate C-C bonding structure, the multiple peaks in the NMR exhibit. Most of the ppm of 5.5 to 6.5 has alkene and aromatic structures, whereas a ppm of 1.5 to 3.5 contains alkane chains. However, when the reaction was gradually progressed, aromatic and alkene group were reduced. When the primary ring-open reaction occurred, the degradation of the norbornene decreased, and the second ring-open reaction was confirmed that aromatic peaks were reduced and the alkyl group increased. Although DCPD use to be cured in nitrogen condition generally, DCPD was shown to be cured even in air condition in case for a short time.

Figure 3 shows the time of processing and heat of reaction with different catalysts in air condition at room temperature. The DCPD exhibited the heat of reaction at about 200°C, and no difference in heat of reaction with different catalysts but takes different curing time. The most active catalyst was tungsten, *W*, whereas the slowest catalyst was molybdenum, *Mo* due to different activity of catalysts. Figure 4 shows the curing time to cure DCPD with different catalysts and reaction time was measured at 200°C. The heat curing time for all 3 catalysts, especially *W*, tends to be reduced sharply up to 80 °C and depending on the catalysts. To cure DCPD, it needed to set up at over 80 °C for stable curing time, and thus the best temperature can be at 80 °C.

Figure 5 shows the mechanical property of the catalyst activity of the air exposure time. The mechanical properties of DCPD were significantly as the air exposure time. The mechanical properties were not changed within 12 hours, and after over 15 hours, sharply decreased. Air exposure time of 18 hours was not cured at all, which means no activity of the catalyst. Since the DCPD resin started to change after more than 12 hours of air exposure time, the polymerization of DCPD does not occur.

Figure 3: Reaction time for polymerization of DCPD with different catalysts.

Figure 4: Curing temperatures for polymerization of DCPD with different catalysts.

Figure 6 shows the mechanical property of tungsten DCPD materials with different compression. Many generated voids from the fracture surface by tensile test were observed for tungsten *p*-DCPD by the RIM method. The air bubble resulted in the deterioration of the mechanical properties of the materials, and the problem is that the air bubble cannot be removed simply by resin injection alone. The applied pressure was 5, 10, and 15 psi to prepare a specimen with tensile and flexural tests. The higher added compression force during fabricating process, the less inside air bubble. Both tensile and

flexural strength increased with decreasing the generation of air bubble. Reduced air bubble can result in better stress transfer to contribute to improved mechanical strength. From the result, the optimum conditions of DCPD fabrication were 15 psi, 300 seconds and 80 °C, respectively.

Figure 5: Mechanical property of W DCPD with different exposed time at atmosphere.

Figure 6: Mechanical property of W DCPD with different compressions.

3.2 RESULTS OF INTERFACIAL, THERMAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTY OF P-DCPD MATERIALS WITH DIFFERENT CATALYST

Figure 7: TGA of DCPD materials with different catalysts.

Figure 8: DSC of DCPD materials with different catalysts.

Figures 7 and 8 show the analysis for crystallinity and thermal stability of the catalyst as the DCPD resin. In case of W DCPD, thermal stability was shown to be lower relatively than other two catalysts of DCPD. This effect can be due to included extra components of rubber inside commercial DCPD.

Mo and Ru catalysts showed a relatively stable TGA results with expecting high degree of cross-linking high polymer. DSC results for Mo or Ru DCPD, TGA exhibited high T_g , whereas W DCPD showed low T_g . In general, T_g of the thermoplastic polymers are lower than 100, but DCPD has high T_g , which means high molecules polymer with high cross-linking degree state.

Table 1: Work of adhesion of DCPD materials with different condition.

	γ_s	γ_s^{LW}	γ_s^+	γ_s^-	γ^d	γ^p	W_a (W DCPD)	W_a (Ru DCPD)	W_a (Mo DCPD)
W DCPD	22.63	11.1	11.3	3.0	19.0	8.1			
Ru DCPD	23.4	13.6	10.1	2.4	21.7	7.8			
Mo DCPD	28.7	17.1	19.1	1.8	29.5	8.6			
Glass fiber (MGF)	32.5	30.6	0.2	4.3	10.5	28.5	52.3	55.4	65.1
Norbordene treatment MGF	31.4	25.2	0.6	15.6	11.2	30.1	64.9	64.2	73.2

Figure 9: Microdroplet test of GF/DCPD materials with different catalysts to get IFSS.

Table 1 shows the work of adhesion of DCPD materials with different catalysts. To know thermodynamic work of adhesion of DCPD composites, their surface energies of the resin and the reinforcing fiber were measured to calculate the interfacial adhesion. The surface energy was measured using a static contact angle for DCPD resins with the different catalysts, whereas the surface energy of MGF was measured by using the dynamic contact angle by Wilhelmy plate method. The higher surface energy was, the higher interfacial adhesion exhibited. Mo DCPD showed the highest work of adhesion with both reinforcements. When one adherent material was high γ^+ , the other adhesive materials must have low γ^- to get high adhesion. γ^+ and γ^- are parameters to attract

each other. It was easy to obtain interfacial adhesion between the DCPD resin and MGF, and thus expected to consistent with overall mechanical strength. The DCPD contains chemically few functional groups since it is composed of most C-C bonds, and when the reinforcing MGF was added to DCPD, the surface treatment of MGF were needed to increase the affinity with DCPD resin. The surface treatment of the MGF was performed by using a silane with norbornene functional groups as shown in Table 1. Surface treated MGF had functional group of norbornene, and DCPD resin had same functional group of norbornene as well, which was consistent to increase interfacial adhesion for both thermodynamically and micromechanically.

Figure 9 shows microdroplet test of GF/DCPD composites with different catalysts to get IFSS using eq. 1. Microdroplet size of DCPD resin with approximately 100 μm was embedded onto MGF surface. The IFSS between the DCPD and MGF with molybdenum catalyst, Mo was highest, and was consistent with thermodynamic work of adhesion, W_a . Tungsten catalyst, W was not easy to cure because the curing process had some problem in air condition. Only three in ten specimens were successful with tungsten catalyst and cured incompletely as rubber state. IFSS using molybdenum, Mo was 46.0 MPa, and tungsten, W was 16.8 MPa, and ruthenium, Ru was 35.4 MPa, respectively. Although DCPD had very stable chemical structure, the interfacial adhesion of MGF decreased. It could be because existing moisture in MGF can prevent to polymerization of DCPD.

Figure 10 shows the fractured surface of norbornene treated MGF of 10wt%/DCPD: (a) W DCPD; (b) Mo DCPD; (c) Ru DCPD. Like IFSS and work of adhesion pullout occurred at the interface between MGF and tungsten DCPD. It means that the interfacial strength was not enough high, but molybdenum and ruthenium had the better interfacial adhesion than tungsten DCPD case. From the comparison of mechanical properties in Table 2, the composition type for producing a composite material can be appropriated by using molybdenum DCPD resin than other tungsten or ruthenium DCPD cases.

Figure 10: The relationship of ILSS and electric resistance change.

Table 2 shows the mechanical properties of DCPD materials with different catalysts. Molybdenum DCPD showed the highest tensile properties. The tensile and flexural strength of the molybdenum DCPD was higher than other two DCPD because of high crystallinity of DCPD. On the other hand, the impact strength was excellent for the DCPD with tungsten catalyst, which showed twice higher at least than other DCPD cases. Ruthenium DCPD showed the lowest mechanical properties, and it was almost similar to epoxy resin. Comparing to epoxy resin, however, ruthenium DCPD has an advantage of curing speed. MGF was added for producing DCPD composite material to show the significant difference in mechanical properties with 3 different catalysts. Tungsten DCPD exhibited low mechanical properties by increasing MGF, whereas molybdenum and ruthenium DCPD showed the increased mechanical properties with adding MGF. When the MGF surface was treated with norbornene, mechanical properties was improved with increasing MGF contents. It is because of interfacial bonding between the MGF and DCPD occurs. Because of both MGF and DCPD contained norbornene groups, which can react with each other to improve the interfacial adhesion.

Table 2: Mechanical property of DCPD materials with different condition.

Type	Tensile strength (MPa)	Flexural strength (MPa)	Impact strength (J/M)
W DCPD	48(5)	75(3)	440(20)
10wt%MGF/WDCPD	39(5)	67(5)	380(50)
20wt%MGF/WDCPD	32(7)	59(8)	320(85)
10 wt% Norbornene treated MGF/ W DCPD	52(6)	80(5)	430(30)
20 wt% Norbornene treated MGF/ W DCPD	50(10)	82(7)	400(40)
Mo DCPD	58(4)	83(2)	258(13)
10wt%MGF/MoDCPD	60(7)	85(6)	220(40)
20wt%MGF/MoDCPD	62(8)	87(7)	189(89)
10 wt% Norbornene treated MGF/ MoDCPD	64(4)	86(4)	250(39)
20 wt% Norbornene treated MGF/ MoDCPD	68(8)	90(8)	230(50)
RuDCPD	43(3)	60(3)	52(14)
10wt%MGF/RuDCPD	45(5)	57(4)	49(15)
20wt%MGF/RuDCPD	46(6)	55(7)	39(25)
10 wt% Norbornene treated MGF/ RuDCPD	50(7)	62(4)	55(18)
20 wt% Norbornene treated MGF/ RuDCPD	52(9)	64(6)	56(23)

4 CONCLUSIONS

Mechanical properties of *p*-DCPD composite materials were studied by mixing MGF reinforcement with different 3 DCPD catalysts, such as W, Mo, Ru, for externally-heavy duty industrial car body and bump. Tensile, flexural and impact strengths were compared for 3 catalysts. Although DCPD is generally known to cure in nitrogen, the curing process could perform in air. For the cured DCPD, the optimum conditions of heating, pressure, maximum exposure time of catalysts were evaluated for the best mechanical properties. Although the reactivity of tungsten catalyst was better than other two catalysts, it was difficult to handle it in air condition due to the instability. When the DCPD fabricated in air condition possibly, the best parameters were with 15 psi at 80 °C until 12 hours exposure time. However, it is good to fabricate as soon as possible. Although molybdenum and ruthenium catalysts were depended on the amount of MGF to increase mechanical properties, the reinforcing was no enhancement effect for tungsten. The reason for this is due to the poor interfacial adhesion between the MGF group and DCPD and thermodynamic work of adhesion showed consistent trend. Surface treated MGF was used to apply silane with norbornene to enhance interfacial adhesion significantly. When MGF reinforced DCPD composite materials can be manufactured

practically, the most suitable catalyst to DCPD was obtained by using molybdenum catalyst for the future heavy industries.

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